

APPLICATION OF ADVANCED MACHINE LEARNING AND DATA ANALYTICS TO ENHANCE ESG PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF THE SUSTAINABLE OIL PALM INDUSTRY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract - The efficient assessment of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance is critical for achieving sustainability, and the global goal of net-zero emissions by 2050. Traditional ESG scoring methods may be effective in various sectors, but are less applicable to the oil palm industry due to their inherent subjectivity. This paper addresses these limitations, by applying a hybrid approach through the use of Machine Learning (ML) and data analytics, to evaluate ESG Performance Indicators in Nigeria's sustainable agriculture sector, specifically within the oil palm industry. The objective is to identify areas of improvement, and reduce the carbon footprint during the oil palm plantation production phase. The study employs a comprehensive data-driven methodology, including Data Collection, Keyword Analysis, Clustering, Topic Modeling, Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) Analysis, Sentiment Analysis, Principal Component Analysis, and Advanced Clustering. These techniques analyze ESG Performance Indicators, focusing on sustainability, compliance, risk, and safety. The results show that advanced analytical methods, can effectively assess ESG performance. Keyword Analysis and Clustering uncover key themes and patterns, while Sentiment Analysis reveals that the farm's ESG practices are generally positive, but highlight the need for improved sustainability measures. The developed ESG scoring system, quantitatively identifies strengths, and areas for improvement, enabling targeted interventions. In conclusion, this hybrid analytical approach proves optimal, for ESG performance assessment in the oil palm industry, and is adaptable for similar evaluations across various sectors globally.

Index Terms - Net Zero Emissions; Sustainable Agriculture; Sentiment Analysis; ESG Rating; Quantitative Assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

The importance of ESG performance assessment in promoting sustainable oil palm plantation farming cannot be overstated. The oil palm industry has significant environmental and social impacts, including deforestation, habitat loss, and greenhouse gas emissions (Murphy, Goggin, and Paterson, 2021). ESG assessment helps identify and mitigate these risks, ensuring sustainable practices and responsible sourcing. In fact, a study by World Wildlife Fund (2020) found that sustainable palm oil production can reduce deforestation and habitat loss by up to 80%.

Oil palm plantations often involve local communities and workers engagement, therefore, to ensure fair labor practices, community engagement, and respect for human rights, ESG assessment is necessary (CFA Institute, 2020).

In the oil palm plantation industry, governance and transparency are essential elements of ESG assessment, fostering accountable and responsible business operations (EY, 2020). Stakeholder pressure plays a significant role, with investors, consumers, and NGOs increasingly pushing for sustainable practices (Deloitte, 2020).

ESG assessment also helps identify potential risks and opportunities, allowing companies to effectively manage their reputation, ensure regulatory compliance, and achieve long-term sustainability SAS. (2020).

To reduce carbon footprint, promote social responsibility, identify potential risks and opportunities in the oil palm plantation that was established four years ago in Nigeria, this study was aimed at examining ESG performance using advanced analytical techniques. This hybrid approach combined data analytics and machine learning found in ESG performance evaluation to overcome the challenges posed by complexity and volume of data involved (Deloitte, 2020) in the oil palm industry.

1.1 Current Practices and Areas of Interest

1.1.1 Sustainable Agriculture Practices

Evaluating current sustainable agriculture practices within oil palm plantations is crucial, as highlighted in various studies. These practices, including climate impact mitigation and waste management, play a vital role in reducing the environmental footprint of palm oil production. (Murphy, Goggin, and Paterson, 2021) emphasize the importance of maintaining biodiversity through buffer zones and using native trees to protect ecosystems and preserve wildlife habitats. Moreover, soil management techniques like cover cropping are shown to prevent erosion, improve fertility, and sustain long-term soil health in oil palm plantations.

1.1.2 Water Management

Previous literature underscores the importance of efficient irrigation systems and rainwater harvesting in reducing water usage and improving water quality. By implementing these practices, plantations can decrease their reliance on external water sources, enhancing their resilience to droughts and minimizing the impact on local water supplies (Zhang, Sheng, Li, and Zhao, 2021). Further studies by Sayara, Basheer-Salimia, Hawamde, and Sánchez (2020) highlights how recycling organic waste back into the soil enhances fertility and reduces waste disposal issues.

1.2 Community Engagement

1.2.1 Employment and Working Conditions

Community engagement is a critical component of ESG assessments, particularly in the oil palm plantation sector. According to Budiani (2020), evaluating employment opportunities, providing living wages, and ensuring safe working conditions are essential for fostering positive relationships with local communities. Furthermore, training and development programs help equip workers with sustainable farming practices and technical skills, thereby contributing to individual and community growth.

1.2.2 HEALTHCARE AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

Study by Maurer, et al. (2020) suggests that healthcare initiatives supporting local facilities and promoting community well-being significantly improve the quality of life for workers and their families. Effective stakeholder engagement, which includes dialogue forums and integrating community input, is crucial for addressing local concerns and ensuring transparency and accountability in decision-making processes.

1.3 Ethical Governance

1.3.1 Governance Framework

The assessment of ethical governance frameworks in oil palm plantations aims to identify areas for improvement, such as clarifying management roles and responsibilities. A robust code of conduct is vital for promoting ethical behavior and decision-making within the organization, as suggested by Meijaard and Sheil (2019).

1.3.2 Regulatory Compliance and Risk Management

Maintaining transparency and accountability requires compliance with global standards and reporting frameworks. Regular risk assessments help identify and mitigate ESG-related risks, while crisis management plans prepare organizations for potential environmental or social incidents (Sharma, 2024) also emphasizes the importance of regional security measures, including strategies to address challenges like kidnapping, to ensure the safety of workers and stakeholders.

1.4 Importance of ESG Considerations

1.4.1 Sustainable Development Goals

Incorporating ESG considerations into large or commercial farm operations is essential for achieving sustainable development. Sustainable Agriculture Network, (2024) highlight that environmentally friendly practices, proactive community engagement, and efficient governance are crucial for the farm's long-term success. These practices contribute not only to the farm's goals but also positively impact society and the environment.

1.5 ESG Performance Metrics

1.5.1 Evaluating ESG Metrics

ESG performance metrics are crucial for assessing ethical and sustainable agricultural practices. According to Zeng and Jiang (2023), these metrics ensure the long-term viability of plantations by maintaining soil health, reducing environmental impact, and enhancing social and economic benefits. Integrating ESG metrics into operations ensures that agricultural practices meet current needs while preserving the environment and promoting community well-being for future generations.

1.6 Sustainable Practices and Long-Term Viability

Previous studies, such as those by El Bilali, Strassner, and Ben Hassen (2021), highlight the benefits of sustainable agriculture for long-term farm viability. These studies emphasize practices such as soil management, climate impact mitigation, and waste management improvements, which contribute to the farm's sustainability and enhance its resilience against environmental and social challenges.

By focusing on these areas, the oil palm plantation industry can align its operations with global ESG standards, ensuring sustainable development and ethical practices that benefit both the environment and local communities.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A hybrid approach combining data analytics and machine learning is necessary in ESG performance evaluation due to the complexity and volume of data involved (Deloitte, 2020). ESG data is often unstructured, fragmented, and sourced from diverse stakeholders (CFA Institute, 2020). The work of (SAS, 2020), has demonstrated Machine learning algorithms to be one of the effective ways to analyze large datasets, identify patterns, and predict ESG performance. Data analytics provides insights into ESG risks and opportunities, while machine learning enhances accuracy and efficiency in evaluation (EY, 2020).

2.1 Advanced Analytical Techniques

In the context of ESG performance assessment of oil palm plantations, various advanced techniques have been employed to extract and analyze data, providing valuable insights into sustainable practices and stakeholder perceptions. Techniques such as keyword analysis, clustering, topic modeling, as seen in the work of Hanny and Resch (2024), Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) analysis, sentiment analysis, and principal component analysis (PCA) have proven effective in these areas (Albalawi, Yeap, and Benyoucef, 2024).

2.2 Keyword and Sentiment Analysis

The use of keyword and sentiment analysis in assessing ESG performance is gaining traction across various industries, including oil palm plantations. These techniques help stakeholders understand the narrative around ESG issues by analyzing large volumes of text data, such as sustainability reports, news articles, and social media posts. It analyzes the frequency and co-occurrence of keywords in ESG-related documents, which helps identify critical aspects of sustainability and understand stakeholder perceptions (Mandas, Lahmar, Piras, and De Lisa, 2023). For example, by examining how often certain terms appear together, researchers can pinpoint key themes and issues that are most relevant to stakeholders. This was proven by Jamil and Asrol (2024) where the work utilized text mining and keyword analysis to assess sustainability practices in the palm oil industry. They extracted key terms from sustainability reports to determine common themes and issues, such as greenhouse gas emissions and community engagement.

It is worth mentioning that Keyword analysis itself doesn't typically rely on a specific mathematical formula but rather on frequency-based measures. However, it often uses techniques like TF-IDF Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) stated in Equations 2.1 to 2.3 to quantify the importance of keywords in a document relative to a corpus.

2.3 Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis, particularly using tools like VADER, provides a deeper understanding of the sentiments associated with ESG practices in the oil palm industry (Hutto and Gilbert, 2015) by analyzing news articles and social media posts to reveal how the public perceives the environmental and social impacts of oil palm plantations. It also analyzes sentiment around company announcements or sustainability initiatives, organizations can gauge their reputation and stakeholder trust concerning ESG performance. This analysis highlights areas that may need attention by gauging the overall sentiment or tone of discussions around ESG practices. Positive sentiments can indicate successful initiatives, while negative sentiments may signal areas requiring improvement or increased transparency.

In a previous study, Rizki (2023) applied sentiment analysis to social media data to assess public perception of palm oil sustainability. They found that sentiment analysis could effectively capture the nuances of public opinion on ESG topics, providing valuable feedback for companies and policymakers.

Sentiment analysis often leverages machine learning algorithms like Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machines (SVM), or neural networks. These models use a more complex mathematical framework involving training data and statistical optimization to classify

text sentiment. These mathematical expressions and techniques form the backbone of keyword and sentiment analysis, helping assess ESG performance by extracting and quantifying insights from text data.

2.4 Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency

While the application of Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) analysis is primarily associated with text mining, information retrieval and natural language processing, it has seen innovative use in various fields, including ESG performance assessment (Qaiser and Ali, 2018). However, specific literature on the direct application of TF-IDF analysis to ESG performance assessment in the oil palm plantation industry may not be widely available. Instead, TF-IDF's role is more commonly found in analyzing large text corpora to derive insights about ESG topics or stakeholder sentiments (Qaiser and Ali, 2018).

The TF-IDF score is a numerical statistic intended to reflect how important a word is to a document in a collection or corpus, and it is based on Equations 2.1 to 2.3.

$$TF(t, d) = \frac{\text{Number of times } t \text{ appears in document } d}{\text{Total number of terms in documents } d} \quad (2.1)$$

where Term Frequency (TF) is the measure of how frequently a term appears in a document. It is often normalized to prevent bias towards longer documents.

On the other hand, the Inverse Document Frequency (IDF) measures how important a term is across the entire corpus. It is used to downscale terms that appear very frequently across documents and are therefore less informative. If the term is very common and appears in many documents, the IDF as expressed in Equation 2.2 will be lower, reducing its weight.

$$IDF(t, D) = \log \left(\frac{\text{Total number of documents } N}{\text{Number of documents containing term } t} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

The TF-IDF Score is, therefore, the product of the Term Frequency, and Inverse Document Frequency as expressed in Equation 2.3. It indicates the importance of a term in a specific document relative to the corpus.

$$TF - IDF(t, d, D) = TF(t, d) * IDF(t, D) \quad (2.3)$$

2.5 TF-IDF Application in ESG Performance Assessment

In the context of ESG performance assessment, TF-IDF can be utilized to analyze text data from reports, news articles, and other documents to identify key themes and issues related to environmental, social, and governance factors. This can include:

Identifying Key ESG Themes: TF-IDF can highlight the most relevant ESG terms in sustainability reports or public disclosures, helping to identify which topics are prioritized by a company or industry.

Stakeholder Sentiment Analysis: Analyzing stakeholder communications or media coverage using TF-IDF can reveal common concerns or positive feedback related to ESG performance.

Comparative Analysis: TF-IDF can compare ESG discourse across different companies or sectors to determine how the oil palm industry aligns with broader sustainability trends.

2.6 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a powerful tool for simplifying complex ESG datasets by reducing their dimensionality while preserving essential information. This technique is instrumental in identifying the most significant variables that influence ESG outcomes, thereby facilitating targeted improvements (Kherif and Latypova, 2020). PCA works by transforming the original variables into a new set of uncorrelated variables called principal components, ordered by the amount of variance they explain.

Mathematically, PCA involves eigenvalue decomposition of the covariance matrix of the data. If \mathbf{X}

\mathbf{X} represents the standardized data matrix, then the principal components are given by:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{XW} \quad (2.4)$$

where \mathbf{W} is the matrix of eigenvectors of the covariance matrix $\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X}$.

Using PCA, ESG data dimensionality can be reduced, allowing for visualization of data points to identify patterns and guide strategic decisions (Institute of Data, 2024). PCA plots can effectively visualize the distribution of ESG data, aiding communication with stakeholders and promoting transparency and accountability.

Further to PCA, a scoring system based on weighted ESG sub-categories can quantitatively assess ESG performance, highlighting strengths and areas needing improvement. This scoring system facilitates continuous monitoring and enhancement of ESG practices (Senadheera, et al, 2021). These approaches offer comprehensive tools for assessing ESG performance in oil palm plantations. They empower stakeholders to make informed decisions, thereby enhancing sustainability and transparency in the industry.

2.7 Topic Analysis

Topic modeling is a type of statistical modeling used to discover abstract topics that occur in a collection of documents. It is particularly useful in identifying hidden thematic structures in large text corpora. One of the most widely used topic modeling techniques is Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA).

LDA is a generative probabilistic model that assumes documents are mixtures of topics, and each topic is a mixture of words. The model uses a Dirichlet distribution to identify the topic distribution for each document and the word distribution for each topic. This approach helps uncover ESG-related topics such as sustainability, labor practices, environmental impact, and community relations by analyzing textual data like sustainability reports and news articles. This aids in identifying key focus areas and emerging issues within the industry, as described by Chauhan and Shah (2022).

2.8 Clustering

Clustering involves grouping similar data points into clusters, making it easier to identify patterns and similarities within ESG data. Some popular clustering techniques include K-Means, DBSCAN, and Gaussian Mixture Models.

2.9 K-Means Clustering

This aims to partition observations into a specified number of clusters, where each observation belongs to the cluster with the nearest mean. The algorithm initializes centroids randomly and iteratively assigns data points to the nearest centroid, recalculating the centroids based on current cluster memberships until convergence. KMeans can categorize ESG data from reports and social media into clusters such as environmental impact, governance issues, and social responsibility practices, allowing companies to target improvements in specific areas, as noted by Rehman, et al. (2019).

2.10 Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN)

DBSCAN is a technique that groups closely packed points and marks points in low-density regions as outliers. It identifies core points with a minimum number of neighbors within a given radius and forms clusters around these core points, labeling non-reachable points as outliers. DBSCAN is useful for identifying outlier behaviors or practices that may indicate ESG risks or exceptional performance, such as unique sustainable practices (Kumar and Reddy, 2016).

2.11 Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM)

GMM model the data as a mixture of multiple Gaussian distributions. This approach assumes the data is generated from several Gaussian distributions with unknown parameters and uses the Expectation-Maximization algorithm to estimate these parameters. GMM can capture complex, multi-modal distributions of ESG data, providing more flexible clustering that accounts for varying degrees of similarity (Bilgrau, 2015).

2.12 Advanced Clustering Techniques

Advanced clustering techniques, such as hierarchical clustering and spectral clustering, provide further insights into ESG data by considering hierarchical structures or relationships among data points. Hierarchical clustering builds a tree-like structure representing nested clusters, useful for visualizing relationships among different ESG issues and identifying broader themes. Spectral clustering uses eigenvectors of a similarity matrix to reduce dimensionality before clustering, capturing complex structures in ESG data that simpler algorithms might miss (Rusu, Boloş and Leordeanu, 2023). The mathematical expression of some of these techniques mentioned here are beyond the scope of this work.

III. MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Material

The data for this study was based on a comprehensive evaluation of ESG performance indicators relevant to sustainable agriculture. These indicators covered various aspects of environmental, social, and governance considerations, as seen in Table 3.1. The framework aimed to assess, the current ESG performance of an oil palm farm in Nigeria and identify areas for improvement. Categories and data points were compiled to encompass a wide range of ESG considerations, ensuring robust analysis.

Data were structured into categories, with exactly thirty (30) elements each, aggregated under these categories, to reflect comprehensive ESG considerations. A data frame was created to ensure consistency and facilitate analysis. Keywords namely, “safety”, “risk”, “sustainability”, “impact” were chosen to represent critical ESG aspects effectively.

The concept of “safety” in ESG performance, encompasses the well-being of individuals, particularly in terms of maintaining safe working conditions, and ensuring transparency within the organization. This aspect is crucial, as it aligns with the broader goals of protecting human rights, and promoting fair labor practices (De Souza Barbosa et al, 2023).

Also “compliance” is another critical dimension, reflecting the organization’s adherence to laws, regulations, and governance standards. It signifies the commitment to uphold legal and ethical standards, ensuring that all operations are conducted, within the regulatory framework, and contributing to corporate governance (Thorisdottir and Johannsdottir, 2020).

Similarly, “Risk” management within ESG focuses on the identification, and mitigation of risks related to environmental, social, and governance factors. This involves proactive measures, to anticipate potential ESG-related challenges, and develop strategies to address them, thus safeguarding the organization’s sustainability, and ethical standing (Yébenes, 2024).

Sustainability pertains to the long-term viability of environmental, social, and economic systems. It emphasizes practices that ensure resources are used efficiently and responsibly, contributing to the overall resilience and longevity, of both the organization and the ecosystems it interacts with (Hosseinpour et al, 2016).

Impact measures the effects of the farm's operations on the environment, and society. It involves assessing how activities influence ecological balance, community well-being, and economic development, aiming to maximize positive outcomes, while minimizing negative consequences (Rosli et al, 2024).

Table 3.1: ESG Performance Indicators for Sustainable Agriculture

ESG Score Card Pillar	Issues	Data Points
Environmental		
	Sustainable Agricultural Practices	Establishment of buffer zones with native tree species
	Agroforestry and Biodiversity	Biodiversity index of the farm area
	Soil Management	Implementation of cover cropping, contour planting, and organic mulching
	Water Management	Soil erosion rate before and after implementation, Soil fertility levels
	Waste Management	Installation of efficient irrigation systems, Rainwater harvesting systems
	Organic Waste Recycling	Water usage metrics, Regular water quality testing
	Wastewater Treatment	Percentage of agricultural waste converted to compost, Reduction in chemical fertilizer usage
	Climate Impact Mitigation	Installation of wastewater treatment facilities, Metrics on water treated and quality of discharge water
	Carbon Footprint Reduction	Greenhouse gas emissions from farm operations, Usage of renewable energy sources.
	Reforestation Projects	Number of trees planted annually, Area of land reforested, Carbon sequestration estimates.
Social		
	Community Engagement and Development	Number of jobs created for local population; Average wages compared to living wage standards, Workplace safety metrics
	Employment Opportunities	Number of training programs conducted annually, Employee participation rates, Improvements in productivity and skill levels
	Education and Training	Investments in local healthcare facilities, Health initiatives launched, Health improvements in the community.
	Healthcare initiatives	Number of forums and meetings held with local stakeholders, Stakeholder satisfaction and feedback metrics
	Stakeholder Engagement	Availability and accessibility of operational reports, Trust and relationship quality with the community
	Inclusive Decision-Making	Compliance with labor laws and international standards, Child labor incidence rates
	Transparency	Implementation of health and safety measures, Occupational health and safety statistics.
	Human Rights and Labor Practices	Structure and roles of the management team, Frequency of governance audits and reviews
	Fair Labor Practices	Development and enforcement metrics of the code of conduct, Incidents of ethical violations reported and resolved

	Safe Working Conditions	Compliance rate with regulations, Frequency and outcomes of compliance audits
Governance		
	Ethical Governance Framework	Frequency and content of ESG performance reports, Stakeholder feedback on ESG reports
	Corporate Governance	Number of risk assessments conducted annually, Identified ESG-related risks and mitigation strategies
	Code of Conduct	Crises management plans in place, Number of crises drills and training sessions
	Compliance and Reporting	Incidence of kidnapping in the region, Security risk level assessments
	Regulatory Compliance	Number of security personnel hired, Installation of surveillance systems, Emergency response protocols
	Risk Management	Number and types of motivated programs implemented, Performance-based incentives distributed, Employee participation
	Risk Assessment	Number of community conflicts reported, Area of conflict
	Crisis Management	Frequency of dialogue sessions with community leaders, Development programs initiated, Compensation agreements
	Insecurity Issues (Kidnapping)	Impact of economic fluctuation on operational costs, Profitability metrics, Income diversification initiatives, Cost control measures.

3.2 Study Workflow

The workflow (Fig.3.1) described in the analysis of ESG performance indicators for sustainable agriculture provides a comprehensive methodology for evaluating, and improving the environmental, social, and governance aspects of farm operations. Each step contributes to a nuanced understanding of how the farm performs in terms of sustainability and offers data-driven insights for targeted improvements.

3.2.1 Step 1: Data Collection and Preparation

In the initial phase, relevant ESG performance indicators were collected, and structured into a data frame, with 30 elements each. This organization ensures a broad and balanced representation of ESG factors. Similar studies often emphasize the importance of comprehensive data collection and structuring to accurately reflect diverse ESG categories (De Souza Barbosa et al, 2023).

3.2.2 Step 2: Keyword Analysis

The selected keywords—safety, compliance, risk, sustainability, and impact—were identified, based on their critical importance to ESG performance. These keywords were counted within the data points, to create columns in the data frame as shown in Table 3.2. This method aligns with previous research emphasizing the role of keyword analysis in understanding thematic priorities, in sustainability assessments (Ali et al, 2023).

Table 3.2: Aggregated Keyword Trends. The scoring system was based on these Aggregated Keyword Trends

Aggregated Keyword Trends	
Safety	3
Compliance	3
Risk	2
Impact	1
Sustainability	0
dtype: int64	

3.2.3 Step 3: Visualization of Keyword Trends

Aggregated keyword counts were visualized, using bar charts, and heatmaps to identify trends, and patterns. This visualization technique is consistent, with methods used by Franconeri et al. (2021), highlighting the significance of visual tools, in identifying thematic frequencies and relationships. Zhu et al. (2021) also emphasize the utility of heatmaps, in demonstrating keyword co-occurrence, providing deeper insights into the interconnectedness of ESG aspects.

3.2.4 Step 4: Text Vectorization

Using Count Vectorizer, data points were transformed into a matrix of keyword counts. This approach is common in text analysis, facilitating the numerical representation of qualitative data for further analysis. It supports the effective application of machine learning techniques, such as clustering and topic modeling.

3.2.5 Step 5: Clustering

The K-Means clustering algorithm was applied to categorize data points into five clusters, visualized through count plots. This technique is widely used, in similar studies to group data based on similarities, allowing for the identification of distinct patterns, within ESG performance (Ahmed et al, 2020).

3.2.6 Step 6: Topic Modeling

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) was employed to uncover underlying topics within the data points. This method extracts, and lists keywords representing individual topics, a process that (Jelodar et al, 2017) have shown to be effective, in identifying thematic structures in text data.

3.2.7 Step 7: TF-IDF Analysis

Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) scores were calculated for keywords, providing a quantitative measure of their importance. This analysis, visualized as a bar chart, helps prioritize ESG factors, as highlighted by Havrlant and Kreinovich (2017). It underscores the relative significance of each keyword, in the context of the entire dataset.

3.2.8 Step 8: Sentiment Analysis

Sentiment analysis using the VADER Sentiment Intensity Analyzer was conducted to assess the sentiment polarity of the data points. This step, visualized through histograms, offers insights into the overall emotional tone associated with different ESG topics (Hutto and Gilbert, 2015).

3.2.9 Step 9: Dimensionality Reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA), was performed on the TF-IDF matrix, enabling visualization in a two-dimensional space, through scatter plots. This dimensionality reduction technique helps simplify complex datasets, while retaining essential information, as discussed by Greenacre).

3.2.10 Step 10: Hierarchical Clustering

Hierarchical clustering using the Ward method was conducted, with a dendrogram plotted, to show relationships among data points. This approach allows for the exploration of data point hierarchies, and their interconnectedness (Murtagh and Legendre, 2014).

3.2.11 Step 11: Advanced Clustering Methods

Advanced clustering methods like DBSCAN, and Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) were applied, providing density-based clustering, and modeling of data points as Gaussian distributions, this is shown in Table 3.2. These methods, highlighted by Vo Van Hai et al. (2022), offer nuanced insights into data structure and distribution.

3.2.12 Step 12: ESG Performance Scoring

Weighted scores were assigned to the ESG subcategories based on analysis results, and these scores were summed, to calculate the final ESG score. This quantitative assessment reflects the integration of analytical results into practical metrics, for performance evaluation (Martiny et al, 2024). Here, the ESG metrics integrated environmental, social, and governance considerations into corporate strategies, assessing sustainability and ethical impacts. Environmental factors included emissions, waste management, water usage, and biodiversity conservation, encouraging strategies that minimized harm and promoted sustainability. Social factors evaluated impacts on employees, communities, and stakeholders, including labor practices, community engagement, and health and safety standards. Governance factors focused on corporate practices like board composition, ethical conduct, transparency, and compliance, ensuring responsible management (Silva, 2024).

3.2.13 Step 13: Assessment and Recommendations

The integrated analytical approach offers a robust framework for evaluating the oil palm farm's ESG performance. By providing clear recommendations for targeted interventions, the study facilitates sustainable and ethical production outcomes. The use of advanced techniques, such as clustering and sentiment analysis as displayed in Fig.3.1, allows for deeper insights into underlying themes and impacts on ESG performance. This comprehensive approach ensures that the farm's practices align with sustainability goals, while identifying areas for improvement.

This methodology (Fig.3.1) is consistent with similar works, that utilize a combination of data collection, text analysis, visualization, and machine learning techniques to assess ESG performance. However, the integration of sentiment analysis, and advanced clustering methods (Fig.3.1) which may have not been used before now, offers unique insights that, distinguish this study from more traditional approaches, highlighting its innovative contribution to, the field of sustainable agriculture evaluation.

Fig.3.1: Adopted Workflow for ESG Performance Evaluation of Oil Palm Plantation

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Keyword Analysis Result

The interpretation of the bar chart in Fig.4.1, shows the frequency of the selected keywords; safety, compliance, risk, sustainability, and impact in the ESG data points with safety and compliance, as the most frequently mentioned words. It is glaring that safety, and compliance appeared three times while risk, impact, and sustainability, occurred two, one, and zero times, respectively as seen in Fig.4.1. The safety and compliance key words, occurrence suggests more emphasis on these aspects in the ESG data. This gives an indication that the oil palm farm takes, critical interest on working in safe working conditions, and adhering to regulations, which are obviously important, for sustainable and ethical production outcomes. The relatively lower mention of "sustainability" and "impact" as shown on the bar chart (Fig.4.1) could also indicate areas where the farm should focus on, particularly for long-term environmental and social impacts improvements. The observed low correlation values suggest that the keywords are relatively independent of each other. Although this is within the data points, it also implies that each keyword represents distinct aspects of the ESG performance. This is without any significant overlap, thereby highlighting the need for a balanced approach to addressing the various ESG aspects to ensure comprehensive sustainability practices (Horvat et al, 2015).

Fig.4.1: Keyword Trends in ESG Data Points

4.2 Clustering Analysis Result

The cluster analysis result in Fig.4.1 produced five distinct clusters namely, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4.

4.2.1 Cluster 0

Cluster 0 shown in Fig.4.1 represents data points from Biodiversity index of the farm area, implementation of cover cropping, contour planting, organic mulching, water usage metrics, and Regular water quality testing. The common theme of the data points relates to environmental monitoring. This is possible through managing environmental factors, specifically biodiversity, soil health, and water usage. All these are essential practices for sustainable agricultural, and ensuring the health of the ecosystem remains in place (Ezugwu et al, 2022).

4.2.2 Cluster 1

Cluster 1 data points represent the establishment of buffer zones (Fig.4.1). This includes the native tree species, soil erosion rate before and after implementation, soil fertility levels, installation of efficient irrigation systems, rainwater harvesting systems, percentage of agricultural waste converted to compost, reduction in chemical fertilizer usage, installation of wastewater treatment facilities, metrics on water treated and quality of discharge water, greenhouse gas emissions from farm operations, usage of renewable energy sources, number of trees planted annually, area of land reforested, carbon sequestration estimates, number of jobs created for local population, average wages compared to living wage standards, workplace safety metrics, number of training programs conducted annually, employee participation rates, improvements in productivity and skill levels, investments in local healthcare facilities, health initiatives launched, health improvements in the community, number of forums and meetings held with local stakeholders, stakeholder satisfaction and feedback metrics, availability and accessibility of operational reports, occupational health and safety statistics, structure and roles of the management team, frequency of governance audits and reviews, development and enforcement metrics of the code of conduct, incidents of ethical violations reported and resolved, compliance rate with regulations, frequency and outcomes of compliance audits, trust and relationship quality with the community, Compliance with labor laws and international standards, child labor incidence rates, implementation of health and safety measures, frequency and content of ESG performance reports, stakeholder feedback on ESG reports, number of risk assessments conducted annually, identified ESG-related risks and mitigation strategies, crisis management plans in place, number of crises drills and training sessions, incidence of kidnapping in the region, and security risk level assessments. The common theme for this Cluster 1 is Comprehensive ESG Management. This covers a broad range of ESG aspects, including environmental sustainability (e.g., waste management, water management, reforestation), social responsibility (e.g., job creation, health initiatives, stakeholder engagement), and governance (e.g., compliance, risk assessments, crisis management). The farm's emphasis on these practices indicates a well-rounded approach to sustainable and ethical production (Ezugwu et al, 2022).

4.2.3 Cluster 2

Cluster 2 data points (Fig.4.1) include compliance rate with regulations, frequency and outcomes of compliance audits, number of security personnel hired, Installation of surveillance systems, and emergency response protocols. The common theme of this cluster is regulatory compliance and security. This focuses on ensuring regulatory compliance and enhancing security measures. These practices are critical for maintaining legal standards, ensuring safety, and protecting assets (Ezugwu et al, 2022).

4.2.4 Cluster 3

Cluster 3 data points (Fig.4.1) include the number of community conflicts reported, areas of conflict, frequency of dialogue sessions with community leaders, development programs initiated and compensation agreements. The common theme is community relations and conflict management. These data points emphasize the importance of managing community relations and addressing conflicts. Regular dialogue with community leaders and implementing development programs are key strategies for fostering good relationships and mitigating conflicts (Ezugwu et al, 2022).

4.2.5 Cluster 4

Cluster 4 data points (Fig.4.1) include the employee engagement, and satisfaction surveys, productivity metrics number, and types of motivational programs implemented, performance-based incentives distributed, employee participation, impact of economic fluctuations on operational costs, profitability metrics, income diversification initiatives, and cost control measures. The common theme is employee well-being, and financial stability. This cluster focuses on employee engagement, satisfaction, and productivity, as well as financial performance, and cost management. Practices aimed at motivating employees, and managing economic challenges, are essential for maintaining a productive and resilient workforce (Ezugwu et al, 2022).

Similarly, the identified Topics from the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model reflect the prominent themes within the ESG data points. Each topic consists of keywords, that are frequently associated with each other within the dataset. The bar chart shows the distribution of ESG data points across the five clusters. This was identified by the K-Means algorithm. Cluster 1 has the highest number of data points, as revealed by the Bar Chart in Fig.4.1. The other clusters have fewer data points. The dominance of Cluster 1 with the highest data points, indicates that many ESG data points share similar characteristics. The presence of multiple Clusters suggests diversity in the ESG practices. It also indicates areas where different strategies or improvements can be applied (Ezugwu et al, 2022).

4.3 Topic Analysis Result

Five topics were identified for the Topic analysis. They are topic 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 as depicted in Table 4.1.

4.3.1 Topic 0: Sustainability, Impact, Compliance, Risk, Safety.

The keywords are Sustainability, which Indicates the farm's focus on sustainable agricultural practices. Impact which reflects the assessment of the environmental and social impact of the farming practices. Compliance which emphasizes adherence to regulations and standards. Risk that Involves the identification, and management of risks associated with farming operations. Safety highlights the importance of ensuring safety for workers and the environment.

This topic looks at the farm's commitment, to sustainable practices, regulatory compliance, risk management, and safety therefore aligning with, the objective of assessing ESG performance; while highlighting areas of improvement, for sustainable outcomes (Naskar et al, 2016).

4.3.2 TOPIC 1: Sustainability, Impact, Compliance, Safety, Risk

This topic has a different order from topic 0, with an emphasis on the order of keywords (Table 4.1). The focus is on sustainability and its impact, compliance with regulations, and ensuring safety while managing risks. This emphasizes the farm's holistic approach to ESG performance (Naskar et al, 2016).

Fig.4.2: ESG Data Point Clusters

4.3.3 TOPIC 2: Sustainability, Compliance, Safety, Risk, Impact

In Topic 2, sustainability continues to be the central theme, while compliance speaks to a strong regulatory adherence. Safety importance is also measured, with Risk measuring the risk management practices. The assessing of the impact, of farming practices is measured by Impact. This topic emphasizes the farm's prioritization of compliance and safety in achieving sustainable outcomes. It also indicates the farm's effort to manage risks, and assessing impacts effectively (Naskar et al, 2016).

4.3.4 TOPIC 3: Sustainability, Impact, Compliance, Safety, Risk

This Topic 3 is like Topic 1 as can be seen in Table 4.1. It reaffirms the farm's dedication to sustainability, impact assessment, compliance, safety, and risk management. Its repetition across multiple Topics suggests their significant presence in the ESG data points (Naskar et al, 2016).

4.3.5 TOPIC 4: Sustainability, Impact, Safety, Risk, Compliance

This Topic has Sustainability as its central theme, while Impact seeks to evaluate the farm practices impact. Safety emphasizes the safety protocols, and the Risk looks at how operational risks are being managed. Compliance looks at the farm's adherence to standards. This Topic highlights the importance of safety and impact evaluation, along with sustainability, risk management, and compliance. It reflects the farm's integrated approach to achieving ESG goals (Naskar et al, 2016). The presence of keywords like "sustainability," "impact," "compliance," "risk," and "safety" across all identified Topics, suggests that these aspects are vital to the farm's ESG practices. The farm is committed to ensuring sustainable agricultural practices. This is evaluated through the impact of its operations, adhering to regulatory standards, managing risks effectively, and prioritizing safety. This approach assesses the ESG performance. This is done through giving insights to recommendations that will lead to improvements for sustainable, and ethical production outcomes (Naskar et al, 2016).

Table 4.1: Identified Topics in ESG Data Points

Topic 0	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4
sustainability	sustainability	sustainability	sustainability	sustainability
impact	impact	compliance	impact	impact
compliance	compliance	safety	compliance	safety
risk	safety	risk	safety	risk
safety	risk	impact	risk	compliance

4.4 TF-IDF Scores

The Bar Chart in Fig.4.3 presents the Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) scores for the keywords, with "Safety," "compliance," and "risk" having the highest scores, which indicates their importance in the data points. The high scores for "safety," "compliance," and "risk" follows the frequency trends (Fig.4.3). It reinforces their significance in ESG considerations, and their significance in the farm's operations, through the highlighting of areas where the farm excels, or needs continuous attention. The low scores recorded against "Sustainability" in Fig.4.3, suggested potential area of focus in the farm's future ESG strategies (Qaiser and Ali, 2018).

The Safety score of 0.066667 as seen in Fig.4.3 indicates, that safety is highly emphasized within the ESG data points, which is proof that the farm prioritizes workers, and environmental safety. Further, it showed that the farm aligned, with the need for safe working conditions, and the implementation of the relevant health and safety measures (Qaiser and Ali, 2018).

Similarly, Compliance with a score of 0.066667 in Fig.4.3, shows a keen focus on adherence to regulations, and standards which is essential for the farm's operations, to meet the legal and industry requirements that are important for sustainable, and ethical production practices (Qaiser and Ali, 2018).

The Risk score of 0.066667 highlights the importance of risk management in the farm's operations. Having an effective risk management, is crucial for mitigating potential negative impacts, on both the environment, and the farm's financial stability (Cumming et al, 2019).

With a score of 0.033333, garnered by Impact (Fig.4.3), it suggests that the farm pays attention to the impact of its activities, but not as that of safety, compliance, and risk. Having a good assessment of the environmental and social impact is important for understanding its broader consequences, in the farm's operations, and for making the needed improvements (Cumming et al, 2019).

On the contrary, with Sustainability recording 0.000000 could be attributed, to possible data issues, or the keyword extraction process where, the term "sustainability" wasn't properly captured despite being a central theme. It could also mean that sustainability might be an underlying theme that is part of other aspects like safety, compliance, and risk, rather than being explicitly stated. The sustainability zero score in Fig.4.3 could suggest that while the farm's practices are sustainable, the term "sustainability" may not be frequently used in the documentation. Another explanation could be that the farm may be emphasizing specific practices, and outcomes (safety, compliance, risk) that contribute to sustainability, without clearly labeling them as such.

Fig.4.3: TF-IDF Scores for Keywords in ESG Data Points

4.5 Sentiment Analysis Results

The histogram in Fig.4.4 shows the distribution of sentiment polarity scores, for the ESG data points. The scores range from -1 to 1, with most data points having neutral to slightly positive sentiment (Fig.4.4). The majority of neutral to positive sentiment suggest generally favorable ESG practices, and perceptions. However, the presence of negative sentiment points highlights areas where improvements are critically needed. Resolving these negative aspects can help enhance the overall ESG performance, and community satisfaction (Ravi, 2015). This Sentiment analysis highlights the general perception of the farm's ESG practices. The positive and neutral sentiments give an indication that many of the farm's practices are looked at as favorable, or acceptable by stakeholders. The negative sentiment points, unveil areas that might be lacking, or problematic, thereby requiring attention and improvement (Ravi, 2015).

The positive sentiment highlights effective and well-received ESG practices. It also Indicates strong compliance with safety, regulatory, and risk management standards. This suggests good community engagement, and environmental stewardship. The Neutral sentiment suggests acceptable, but potentially improvable ESG practices. It highlights areas that meet basic requirements but may lack innovation or excellence. Contrarily, the negative sentiment (Fig.4.4) points to areas needing significant improvement, or reform which could be related to issues in areas, such as waste management, stakeholder engagement, or transparency. The Identification and resolution of these negative points can enhance the farm's overall ESG performance.

Fig.4.4: Sentiment Analysis of ESG Data Points

Table 4.2 below shows the results of the Sentiment analysis, of the different ESG Categories. The result shows the sentiment polarity scores for various ESG categories that relate to the farm. Each of these categories is associated with a sentiment score. The score ranges from -1 (depicting a negative sentiment) to 1 (depicting a positive sentiment), with the scores close to 0 indicating neutral sentiment.

The following Sustainable Agricultural Practices, Agroforestry and Biodiversity, Soil Management, Water Management, Organic Waste Recycling, Climate Impact Mitigation, Inclusive Decision-Making, Human Rights and Labor Practices, Safe Working Conditions and Ethical Governance Framework all have a score of 0.0000 as shown in Table 4.1. This indicates a neutral sentiment. It also suggests that the current practices are neither highly accepted nor criticized. They are seen with a balanced view, that reflects the average perceptions. They have no strong opinions on soil management practices. This does not depict whether it is exceptional or problematic either. They are at the basic standards level. They could be considered adequate, but not outstanding.

Waste Management has a value of 0.4215 in Table 4.2. This indicates a positive sentiment, which has favorable views, on the farms' waste management practices. This therefore suggests effectiveness and efficiency. The Carbon Footprint Reduction has a value of 0.2732. This shows a slightly positive sentiment. It indicates that the carbon footprint reduction efforts are viewed positively. They also have room for improvement. The Reforestation Projects have a value of 0.0772. The projects are appreciated but will require more robust efforts. The Community Engagement and Development has a value of 0.6249. This highlights a strong approval of the farms' community engagement and development initiatives. The Employment Opportunities value is 0.3818. Education and Training score is 0.4215. Healthcare Initiatives score is 0.4939. Stakeholder Engagement score is 0.5106. Transparency value is 0.6808, while Risk Management score is 0.3818. They all indicate positive sentiments. This means that the farm is viewed favorably,

with good approval ratings and effective practices. The ESG Reporting has a score of 0.7096. This suggests a positive sentiment of strong approval of ESG reporting practices for the farm. The Fair Labor Practices score is 0.1531. Compliance and Reporting has a value of 0.0772. Regulatory Compliance has a value of 0.0250. Crisis Management has a score of 0.2732 and Insecurity Issues (Kidnapping) has a value of 0.2732. They all indicate a slightly positive sentiment, with general favorable approval, but identifies room for improvement.

Wastewater Treatment has a value of -0.4215, as can be seen on the histogram (Table 4.2), while Corporate Governance has a value of -0.4404. Code of Conduct has a value of -0.8360. The value for Risk Assessment is -0.5754. They all indicate negative sentiment, and clear dissatisfaction or concerns. They all highlight a need for far-reaching improvement. The results from this sentiment analysis highlight the farm's strengths. It also indicates areas that need improvement in its ESG practices. The categories with positive sentiment suggest the effective practices, that are well-received by the various stakeholders. The negative sentiment categories suggest areas that need urgent attention. These are areas where far-reaching improvements, or enhancements, need to be made. The neutral sentiments suggest practices that are acceptable but could benefit from further enhancement. This can be the sentiments towards more positive perceptions (Ravi, 2015).

Table 4.2: Sentiment Analysis Results for ESG Categories

Sentiment Analysis Results	
Category	Sentiment
Sustainable Agricultural Practices	0.0000
Agroforestry and Biodiversity	0.0000
Soil Management	0.0000
Water Management	0.0000
Waste Management	0.4215
Organic Waste Recycling	0.0000
Wastewater Treatment	-0.4215
Climate Impact Mitigation	0.0000
Carbon Footprint Reduction	0.2732
Reforestation Projects	0.0772
Community Engagement and Development	0.6249
Employment Opportunities	0.3818
Education and Training	0.4215
Healthcare Initiatives	0.4939
Stakeholder Engagement	0.5106
Inclusive Decision-Making	0.0000
Transparency	0.6880
Human Rights and Labor Practices	0.0000
Fair Labor Practices	0.1531
Safe Working Conditions	0.0000
Ethical Governance Framework	0.0000
Corporate Governance	-0.4404
Code of Conduct	-0.8360
Compliance and Reporting	0.0772
Regulatory Compliance	0.0258
ESG Reporting	0.7096
Risk Management	0.3818
Risk Assessment	-0.5754
Crisis Management	0.2732
Insecurity Issues (Kidnapping)	0.2732

4.6 PCA Result

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) scatter plot in Fig.4.5 shows the visualization of the ESG data points. They are in a two-dimensional space and defined by the first two principal components. The cluster assignments determine the color of the points. The plot shows the separation of the ESG data points into distinct clusters. They indicate variability in the ESG practices. This separation helps to identify specific areas where the targeted improvements can be made. To this end, points that are shown as outliers may represent unique practices. They can also represent issues that need attention (Mishra et al, 2017). The various data points are grouped into five clusters as shown in Fig.4.5. They are indicated by the different colors (purple for cluster 0, blue for cluster 1, teal for cluster 2, green for cluster 3, and yellow for cluster 4). Each of the clusters represents a grouping, of ESG data

points with similar characteristics. The two axes are the x-axis (Principal Component 1), and y-axis (Principal Component 2). They are linear combinations of the original features, that maximize the variance of the data. Principal Component 1 highlights the most variance in the data. Principal Component 2 explains the second most variance.

The plot displays a clear separation between the various clusters (Fig.4.5). This indicates that the principal components effectively capture the variance in the data. Cluster 1, which is blue in color is densely packed. It indicates a higher concentration of similar data points. The other clusters are more dispersed. The PCA plot helps to identify the patterns, and trends in the ESG data points. This enables a deeper understanding of the underlying factors that contribute to the farm's ESG performance. This analysis highlights the farm's strengths. It also shows its weaknesses, in different ESG categories, thereby guiding targeted improvements (Mishra et al, 2017). The clustering of data points reveals common themes. It also highlights practices within each cluster. For instance, clusters might represent different levels of compliance. It could also portray risk management, sustainability practices, or stakeholder (Mishra et al, 2017). By examining the clusters, one can assess the farm's performance across various ESG dimensions. This clustering information can be used to benchmark the farm's practices against industry standards, or best practices (Hloušková and Lekešová, 2020).

The insights gained from PCA, and clustering can inform strategic decision-making. This can help the farm to prioritize actions needed. Especially to address areas where the data points show negative or neutral sentiment, as identified in the sentiment analysis (Mishra et al, 2017). For example, if a cluster shows poor performance in risk management, strategic and targeted interventions can be designed, to mitigate risks and improve compliance in that area (Cumming et al, 2019). The use of the PCA technique can enhance the transparency, and comprehensiveness of ESG reporting. Using it allows stakeholders to visualize and understand the farm's ESG performance more effectively. This will foster trust and accountability. The PCA plot (Fig.4.5) provides a useful visual representation of the ESG data points' distribution. It also showcases their clustering, by offering valuable insights into the farm's ESG practices. The insights gained can drive improvements in sustainable agriculture practices. This ultimately contributes to enhanced ESG performance.

Fig.4.5: PCA of ESG Data Points

4.7 Hierarchical Clustering Result

The dendrogram in Fig.4.6, displays the hierarchical clustering of the ESG data points. It shows the relationships between them based on their similarity. The hierarchical clustering gives a detailed view of how ESG data points are grouped together. It also offers insights into the underlying structure of the ESG practices. The dendrogram branches indicate the degree of similarity between data points. This can guide the development of customized ESG strategies for different clusters (Murtagh and Legendre, 2014). The dendrogram visually represents the hierarchical clustering of the ESG data points. It shows how they are grouped based on their similarities. The key components of the dendrogram like the leaves or data points, are depicted by the numbers on the x-axis. They represent individual ESG data points. Each leaf corresponds to a data point in the dataset. The branches connect the leaves and indicate the hierarchical relationships between these data points. The branches length represents the distance (or dissimilarity) between the data points. Shorter branches indicate more similar data points. The y-axis represents the Euclidean distance or dissimilarity between the data points. The height at which two branches merge indicates the level of similarity between the clusters they represent. Lower mergers indicate higher similarity.

Horizontal cuts across the dendrogram at different heights can be used to determine the number of clusters. For example, a cut at a height of 1.0, might reveal several distinct clusters. Each of them contains data points with high similarity. The degree of similarity is shown by the data points or clusters that merge at a lower height. They are more like each other than those that are merged at a higher height. This can be used to identify groups of ESG practices that are closely related. The hierarchical clustering and dendrogram provide valuable insights into the structure of ESG practices. The grouping can be understood by Identifying natural groupings of ESG practices. Especially when they share common characteristics or themes. For instance, practices related to "compliance" and "safety" might cluster together. This indicates a focus on regulatory adherence, and worker protection (Murtagh and Legendre, 2014). The clustering information can be used to develop tailored ESG strategies, for different groups of practices.

For example, strategies to improve "compliance" might be different, from those needed to enhance "sustainability" practices. It can also be used for the Identification of specific clusters that require targeted improvements. If a cluster shows poor performance, especially in areas like "risk management" or "corporate governance," focused interventions can be designed to address these (Murtagh and Legendre, 2014). The hierarchical clustering results (Fig.4.6) can be used to enhance ESG reporting. It can also be used in communication with stakeholders. This can help in clearly communicating how different ESG practices are related. As well as how improvements in one area can positively impact others. The hierarchical clustering with the dendrogram provides a comprehensive view, of the relationships between ESG data points. This information is crucial for developing effective ESG strategies. It is also critical for improving practices and communicating the farm's ESG performance to stakeholders.

Fig.4.6: Hierarchical Clustering Dendrogram

4.8 Advanced Clustering Results

Two advanced clustering methods were used namely Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN), Clustering, and GMM Clustering. The DBSCAN clustering algorithm groups data points based on their density. This is shown in Fig.4.7. It identifies clusters of high density, and marks points in low-density regions as noise (Kazemi and Soleimani, 2024). The result of this technique shows that most data points fall into Cluster 0, as can be seen in Fig.4.7. It indicates a single dense group of ESG practices. Smaller clusters (1, 2, and 3) represent less dense regions or outliers. A few points fall into Cluster -1, marked as noise or outliers. The concentration of data points in Cluster 0, suggests that most ESG practices at the farm, are consistently applied and form a cohesive group. The smaller clusters and noise points indicate areas where practices may differ or need special attention. These outliers and unique cases can highlight specific areas for tailored improvements (Kazemi and Soleimani, 2024).

The Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM), clustering algorithm as shown in Fig.4.8, assumes that the data points are generated from a mixture of several Gaussian distributions. It uses probability to assign data points to clusters as showed in (Kazemi and Soleimani, 2024).

Cluster 1 contains most of the data points as can be seen in Fig.4.7. This indicates a significant grouping of similar ESG practices. Smaller clusters (0, 2, 3, and 4), represent less prevalent ESG practices or unique cases. The results from GMM clustering (Fig.4.8), corroborate the findings from DBSCAN, and K-Means clustering. The dominant Cluster 1 signifies a central group of ESG practices,

while the smaller clusters identify areas where practices vary. GMM helps us to understand the probability, and distribution of different ESG practices, ensuring unique cases are not overlooked, and are given proper attention (Kazemi and Soleimani, 2024).

The advanced clustering methods, including DBSCAN and GMM highlight the presence of a dominant cluster (Cluster 0 in DBSCAN and Cluster 1 in GMM). Both show that most ESG practices are consistent and form a central group. This consistency is crucial for maintaining the overall ESG performance, and achieving sustainability goals [54]. The identification of smaller clusters, and outliers' points to areas, where practices deviate from the norm. These deviations can indicate specific issues. It can also suggest unique cases that require tailored improvements, or interventions [54]. By focusing on the smaller clusters and outliers, the farm can develop targeted strategies. These strategies will address specific ESG challenges. This approach ensures that all aspects of ESG performance are optimized, and no issues are left unaddressed (Kazemi and Soleimani, 2024).

The clustering methods provide, a framework for continuous monitoring, and evaluation of ESG practices. Regular analysis can help identify emerging trends. It can also identify new outliers, and areas for improvement, ensuring ongoing enhancement of ESG performance. By integrating these advanced analytical techniques, the farm can achieve more precise and effective ESG strategies. This will ultimately lead to sustainable and ethical production outcomes. The Data Frame in Table 4.3 provides a detailed analysis of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) data points. It incorporates several advanced analytical techniques. The ESG scores were assigned to each ESG sub-category. It was based on the analysis results as shown in Table 4.4. Each weight reflects their importance where 40%, 30%, 30% weighted scores are assigned to Environmental, Social, and Governance, respectively. The Final ESG Score, which is a weighted score, was summed. This was done to calculate the final ESG score. This provided a quantitative assessment of the farm's performance.

Fig.4.7: DBSCAN Clustering of ESG Data Points

Fig.4.8: GMM Clustering of ESG Data Points

Table 4.3: ESG Data Frame with Additional Analysis

ESG Data Frame with Additional Analysis						
Category						
0	Sustainable Agricultural Practices					
1	Agroforestry and Biodiversity					
2	Soil Management					
3	Water Management					
4	Waste Management					
Data Points					Safety	Compliance
0	Establishment of buffer zones with native trees				0	0
1	Biodiversity index of the farm area				0	0
2	Implementation of cover cropping, contour plowing				0	0
3	Soil erosion rate before and after implementation				0	0
4	Installation of efficient irrigation systems				0	0
	Risk	Sustainability	Impact	Cluster	Sentiment	PCA1
0	0	0	0	1	0.0000	3.64E-17
1	0	0	0	1	0.0000	1.44E-16
2	0	0	0	1	0.0000	7.42E-17
3	0	0	0	1	0.0000	9.60E-17
4	0	0	0	1	0.4215	9.36E-17
	PCA2	DBSCAN Cluster	GMM Cluster			
0	-1.72E-17	0	1			
1	-6.58E-17	0	1			
2	-4.00E-17	0	1			
3	-1.73E-16	0	1			
4	-1.44E-17	0	1			

Table 4.4: ESG Score Summary

ESG Score Summary Table			
Category	Sub-Category	Score (out of 100)	Weighted Score
Environmental Impact (40%)	Sustainability Practices	50	
	Waste Management	70	
	Biodiversity Enhancement	60	
	Soil Management	70	
	Water Management	65	
Average Environmental Impact Score		63	
Weighted Environmental Impact Score			25.2
Social Benefits (30%)	Community Engagement	80	
	Employment Opportunities	75	
	Training Programs	70	
	Healthcare Initiatives	85	
Average Social Benefits Score		77.5	
Weighted Social Benefits Score			23.25
Governance Structures (30%)	Ethical Governance Framework	60	
	Compliance Frameworks	65	
	Risk Management	70	
	Corporate Governance	50	
Average Governance Structures Score		61.25	
Weighted Governance Structures Score			18.375
Final ESG Score			66.83

4.9 Discussion

This study stands out in the landscape of ESG analysis within the agricultural sector by employing a unique combination of methodologies and offering fresh insights that both align with and diverge from existing research. O'Hearn et al. (2023) made significant strides in assessing ESG practices across various agricultural companies by utilizing Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and hierarchical clustering. Their approach simplified the analysis by condensing numerous ESG indicators into key components. In contrast, this study not only employs PCA and clustering but also introduces novel techniques such as Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) analysis, which have not been previously applied in ESG performance assessments within the oil palm plantation industry.

While Chopra et al. (2024) concentrated on governance practices within agricultural supply chains, this study provides a comprehensive analysis that includes environmental and social dimensions alongside governance. This broader scope reflects a more integrated approach to ESG evaluation, distinguishing it from narrower studies.

The recommendations offered by Ayompe et al. (2020) for improving sustainability metrics in palm oil production share similarities with this study's emphasis on data-driven, practical recommendations. Both studies strive to pinpoint areas for enhancing sustainable agricultural practices. However, this study's use of advanced quantitative methods provides a more robust framework for such recommendations.

Naskar et al. (2016) diverged by utilizing sentiment analysis and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to evaluate social impacts, whereas this study's reliance on quantitative methods like PCA and clustering offers a more comprehensive evaluation of ESG performance. This methodological difference highlights this study's focus on providing a more nuanced and quantitative understanding of ESG issues.

Furthermore, studies like Taghian et al. (2015) integrated stakeholder interviews with quantitative analysis, aligning with this study's approach of combining qualitative and quantitative findings. This shared commitment underscores a holistic view of ESG practices, emphasizing the need to highlight strengths and identify areas for improvement.

This study has shown its unique contributions to advancing ESG research in agricultural contexts. The integration of innovative analytical techniques and the comprehensive scope of this study underscore its distinctiveness and commitment to pushing the boundaries of ESG analysis in the oil palm plantation industry.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This work provides an in-depth analysis of the integration of advanced analytical techniques, to enhance the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance, in sustainable agriculture. It uses a case study of an oil palm farm in Nigeria, which has been evaluated across various ESG dimensions.

The key findings from the study can be grouped into three subcategories. They are Environmental Impact, Social Benefits and Governance Structures. The Environmental Impact subcategory has the farm's sustainability practices. This subcategory score was seen to be very low, with a significant gap in explicitly stated sustainability efforts. This indicates a need for more focused, and transparent sustainability initiatives. The positive sentiment on waste management indicates effectiveness in waste management practices. Although there is room for enhancement in organic waste recycling, and wastewater treatment, for the Social Benefits subcategory, the farm has shown strong community engagement efforts. Having positive sentiment around employment opportunities, training programs, and healthcare initiatives. The result also shows that there is a need for greater transparency, and more extensive stakeholder engagement, to build trust within the community.

On the Governance Structures subcategory, the farm has a basic ethical governance framework in place. Although it requires improvements, strengthening the code of conduct, enhancing compliance and reporting frameworks, and addressing regional security challenges, through comprehensive risk assessments are essential. The hybrid approach and advanced analytical found in machine learning has the potential to further integrate sustainability explicitly into the farm's practices.

5.1 Recommendations

Based on the interpretational outcomes for all the models analyzed, this work therefore recommends the Implementation of buffer zones with native tree species to maintain and enhance biodiversity. The farm should adopt advanced soil management techniques, such as cover cropping, contour planting, and organic mulching, to prevent erosion and enhance soil fertility. It should develop efficient irrigation systems, and rainwater harvesting to reduce water usage, and improve water quality. It should implement strategies to enhance organic waste recycling, and wastewater treatment to minimize chemical fertilizer usage, and ensure treated water is safely discharged. There should be explicit documentation, and emphasis on sustainability practices, to improve transparency and stakeholder trust. Establishment of forums for dialogue with local stakeholders, to integrate their input into farm operations, and ensure greater transparency should be pursued.

This work also identifies the need for additional training programs that will focus on sustainable farming practices, technical skills development, and safety protocols. Investments should be continuously expanded, in local healthcare facilities and initiatives, to improve community well-being. There should be a deliberate drive to develop and enforce a comprehensive code of conduct, promoting ethical behavior and decision-making. Implementation of improved compliance and reporting frameworks, to adhere to local, national, and international environmental, and social standards should be pursued. Conduct comprehensive risk assessments, and establish mitigation strategies, to enhance security measures, particularly in addressing regional security challenges, like kidnapping. Regularly conduct risk assessments, and ESG performance evaluations, using advanced analytical techniques, to identify emerging trends, and areas for improvement. Utilize advanced analytical insights to enhance the transparency, and comprehensiveness of ESG reporting, fostering trust, and accountability among stakeholders. Focus on areas with neutral, or negative sentiment, such as wastewater treatment, and corporate governance, to address concerns and improve overall ESG performance.

By implementing these recommendations, the oil palm farm can enhance its ESG performance, thereby contributing positively to the environment and society. This will enable it to achieve long-term sustainability, and ethical production outcomes. The integration of advanced analytical techniques provides a robust framework for continuous improvement. This will ensure that the farm remains a leader in sustainable agricultural practices.

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